

Vanadates of Cerium and Praseodymium-An Electrometric Study

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Manuscript received 14 January 1972, revised October 1972, accepted 12 January 1973.

The stoichiometry of the compounds formed by the interaction of cerous nitrate and praseodymium chloride with different alkali vanadates (ortho, pyro and meta) has been investigated by means of pH, potentiometric and conductometric titrations. The breaks and inflections in the titration curves provide cogent evidence for the formation of ortho- $X_2O_3 \cdot V_2O_5$, pyro- $2X_2O_3 \cdot 3V_2O_5$ and meta vanadates $X_2O_3 \cdot 3V_2O_5$ at different pH ranges. -X- represents Ce(III) and Pr(III).

THE investigations on the reaction of vanadium (V) oxy-anions with heavy metal salts at different pH levels have been the subject of considerable interest in this laboratory due to their peculiar behaviour and have yielded significant results on the poly-vanadates of several metals.¹⁻³ The literature on cerium (III) and praseodymium vanadates is meagre and most of the earlier workers had confined themselves to the preparative and analytical study of these compounds. Brixner and Abramson⁴ from X-ray study of $Ce_2O_3-V_2O_5$ system, reported the formation of $CeVO_4$. Arbit and Serebrennikov⁵ obtained the precipitate of $Ce_4(V_6O_{17}) \cdot 48H_2O$ and $CeVO_4$ by mixing ammonium orthovanadate and metavanadate with cerous nitrate respectively. Crystallographic parameters of $Ce_2V_{10}O_{28} \cdot 28H_2O$ were reported by Glazyrin and Ivakin⁶. In view of the insufficient and conflicting details of reports of earlier workers on the composition of these vanadates and in absence of any electrometric data on the subject, it was considered worthwhile to study the formation and compositions of Cerium (III) and praseodymium vanadates, obtained by the interaction of cerous nitrate and praseodymium chloride with alkali vanadates at different pH levels by means of electrometric techniques which have provided reliable results on the composition of metal vanadates¹⁻³. Hence the present investigation has been undertaken.

Experimental

Anal.R(B.D.H.) reagents, Praseodymium chloride, Cerous nitrate, Vanadium pentoxide, Sodium hydroxide, and Hydrochloric acid were used and their solutions prepared in air free conductivity water.

Standard solution of sodium orthovanadate was prepared by digesting one mole of V_2O_5 in boiling solution of NaOH containing six moles of it. The alkali pyro and meta vanadate solutions were prepared by adding two and four moles of HCl to a solution containing one mole of orthovanadate at 100° respectively.

pH and e.m.f. measurements were carried out on a Cambridge null Deflection type pH meter using a wide range glass electrode and platinum electrode in

conjunction with S.C.E. The e.m.f. and pH were noted after each addition of the titrant in small increments, which were further decreased in the region of the end point and plotted against the volume of the titrant added. The end points were determined from the sharp inflections in titration curves and the maximum values of dpH/dV and dE/dV .

An electronic eye indicator type conductometer, was used for conductance measurements. The corrected conductances were plotted as a function of the ml. of titrant added and the end points were judged from the breaks in the titration curves.

Using different concentrations of reactants, a series of glass electrode, e.m.f. and conductometric titrations were carried out both by the direct and reverse methods i.e., when $Ce(NO_3)_3$ or $PrCl_3$ solution from the microburette was added to different alkali vanadate solution and *vice versa*. The same strengths of reagents were employed in all measurements for the sake of comparison of results, which have been summarised in tables 1 and 2. Four figures illustrating direct and reverse pH and e.m.f. titration curves have been given. The conductometric titration curves are excluded for the sake of brevity.

Discussion

Vanadium (V) oxy-anions, which figure prominently in the discussions on isopoly acids, exist in solution as four different species⁷⁻⁹ viz., $(VO_4)^{3-}$, $(V_2O_7)^{4-}$, $(VO_3)^{1-}$ and $(V_{10}O_{27})^{4-}$ in the vicinity of pH 12, 10, 7 and 4.5 respectively. The investigations on the reactions of these anions with cerium(III) and praseodymium salts at different pH levels have been carried out by means of pH, potentiometric and conductometric titrations to ascertain whether similar salts of these metals may be precipitated as a result of double decomposition.

Orthovanadate titrations: The pHs of $Ce(NO_3)_3$, $PrCl_3$ and $3Na_2O \cdot V_2O_5$ solutions were 3.5, 5.0 and 11.7 respectively. In the case of direct titrations when cerous and praseodymium salt solutions were used as the titrant (Figs. 1 and 3, curve 1), a gradual decrease in pH was observed until at the stoichiometric end point (where $X_2O_3 : V_2O_5$ are in the

TABLE 1

Molarity of solutions [M/]		Calc.	Equivalence point (ml) Observed from		
			E.M.F.	pH	Cond.
Ce(NO ₃) ₃	3Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅	Direct orthovanadate titrations figs. 1 and 2, curve 1			
	10 150	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
	25 500	3.00	2.95	4.00	3.05
	50 800	3.75	3.80	3.80	3.60
Reverse orthovanadate titrations figs. 1 and 2, curve 2					
	50 10	3.00	3.00	2.95	3.05
	300 50	2.50	2.55	2.50	2.45
	750 200	4.00	3.95	4.05	3.95
Ce(NO ₃) ₃	2Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅	Direct pyrovanadate titrations figs. 1 and 2, curve 3			
	10 100	4.00	3.90	3.95	4.00
	25 300	3.33	3.35	3.30	3.30
	50 500	4.00	3.90	3.90	3.85
Reverse pyrovanadate titrations fig. 1 and 2, curve 4					
	60 10	3.75	3.75	3.75	3.80
	300 40	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.90
	750 150	4.50	4.60	4.45	4.35
Ce(NO ₃) ₃	Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅	Direct meta vanadate titrations figs. 1 and 2, curve 5			
	10 80	2.50	2.50	2.40	2.65
	60 300	4.00	2.90	3.90	4.10
	120 750	3.20	3.15	3.10	3.10

TABLE 2

Molarity of solutions [M/]		Calc.	Equivalence points (ml) Observed from		
			pH	E.M.F.	Cond.
PrCl ₃	3Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅	Direct orthovanadate titrations figs. 3 and 4, curve 1			
	10 200	3.00	3.05	3.05	3.10
	40 500	4.80	4.95	4.80	4.75
	60 1000	3.60	3.70	3.70	3.55
Reverse orthovanadate titrations figs. 3 and 4, curve 2					
	50 10	3.00	2.95	3.05	3.10
	400 100	3.75	3.70	3.80	3.70
	750 200	4.00	3.85	3.95	3.90
PrCl ₃	2Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅	Direct pyrovanadate titrations figs. 3 and 4, curve 3			
	10 100	4.00	3.95	4.00	3.90
	25 400	2.50	2.40	2.55	2.60
	60 1000	3.00	2.90	2.90	2.95
Reverse pyrovanadate titrations figs. 3 and 4, curve 4					
	75 10	3.00	3.00	2.90	2.90
	300 50	3.75	3.80	3.65	3.60
	750 150	4.50	4.60	4.55	4.40
PrCl ₃	Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅	Direct metavanadate titrations figs. 3 and 4, curve 5			
	10 60	3.33	3.25	3.30	3.20
	100 500	4.00	3.95	4.05	3.90
	150 800	3.75	3.65	3.65	3.70
Reverse metavanadate titrations, figs. 3 and 4 curve 6					
	120 10	3.75	3.85	3.85	3.70
	500 50	4.50	4.50	4.65	4.40
	900 80	4.00	4.15	4.10	4.05

ratio (1 : 1), a steep fall in pH was noted corresponding to the formation of cerous and praseodymium orthovanadates in the pH range (6.5-9.0). In the case of inverse titrations (Figs. 1-3, curve 2) a sharp jump in pH is obtained at the stoichiometric end point suggesting the formation of similar compounds.

Potentiometric titrations (Figs. 2 and 4, curves 1, 2) and conductometric titrations also confirm the

results obtained from pH measurements. The reactions can be stated as follows:—

Pyrovanadate titrations: The sodium pyrovanadate solution was prepared as described earlier. Figs.

Figs. 1. and 2. Direct and Reverse pH and E.M.F. titrations between $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and alkalinanadates.
ml of M/

Curve 1—10 $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	50 $3\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$
Curve 2—10 $3\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$	50 $3\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$
Curve 3—10 $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	100 $2\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$
Curve 4—10 $2\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$	60 $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$
Curve 5—10 $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	80 $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$

Figs. 3 and 4. Direct and Reverse pH, and E.M.F. titrations between PrCl_3 and alkalinanadates.
ml of M/

Curve 1—10 PrCl_3	200 $3\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$
Curve 2—10 $3\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$	50 PrCl_3
Curve 3—10 PrCl_3	100 $2\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$
Curve 4—10 $2\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$	75 PrCl_3
Curve 5—10 PrCl_3	60 $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$
Curve 6—10 $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$	120 PrCl_3

1 to 4, curves 3 and 4 illustrate the changes occurring in pH and e.m.f. during the course of reaction between alkali pyrovanadate and cerous and praseodymium salt solutions. The equivalence point was marked by sharp inflection and pronounced maxima in

dpH/dV and dE/dV which suggest the formation of cerous pyrovanadate $2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ and praseodymium vanadate $2\text{Pr}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ in the pH range (5.0-6.3). The result of the conductometric titrations also support the formation of identical compounds.

The formation can be represented as :

Metavanadate titrations: The alkali meta vanadate solution was prepared as described earlier. When PrCl_3 and $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ were used as titrant, the $p\text{H}$ and e.m.f. decrease rapidly in the beginning. The equivalence point obtained from titration curves (figs. 1 to 4, curve 5) indicate that $(\text{X})^{3+}$ and $(\text{VO}_3)^{1-}$ ions react in the ratio of 1 : 3, and reveal for formation of praseodymium and cerium (III) metavanadates in the $p\text{H}$ range (4.0–4.8). In the case of inverse titrations, when $\text{Na}_2\text{O.V}_2\text{O}_5$ solution was added to $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solution in the cell, the $p\text{H}$, e.m.f. and conductance change rapidly in the beginning and the curves do not exhibit any appreciable break or inflections at the stoichiometric end point. The addition of sodium metavanadate to PrCl_3 solution, causes an initial decrease in $p\text{H}$ and e.m.f. (Figs. 3 and 4, curve 6) till about half the volume of titrant required for the precipitation of praseodymium meta vanadate is added. The initial decrease in $p\text{H}$ and e.m.f. values are ascribed to the presence of hydrolysed acid from PrCl_3 . Later on, with the progress of the reaction, $p\text{H}$ and e.m.f. begin to rise and an upward inflection is obtained at the end point corresponding to the formation of $\text{Pr}_2\text{O}_3.3\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$. The well defined breaks in conductometric titration curves evidenced the

formation of similar compounds. The reactions can be represented as under :

Analytical investigations were also carried out with a view to substantiate the electrometric results. The precipitates of different vanadates were analysed for metal and vanadium contents using standard methods of analysis. The results of analytical study were found to be in close agreement with the compositions obtained from electrometric data.

It is apparent from the present study that cerous and praseodymium salts with different alkali vanadates yield corresponding salts, namely ortho- $\text{X}_2\text{O}_3.V_2\text{O}_5$; Pyro- $2\text{X}_2\text{O}_3.3\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ and meta $\text{X}_2\text{O}_3.3\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ -Vanadates at $p\text{H}$ ranges (6.5–9.0), (5.0 to 6.3) and (4.0–4.8) respectively.

Acknowledgement

Our thanks are due to Prof. R. M. Advani, Principal, Malaviya Regional Engineering College, Jaipur for providing research facilities.

References

1. R. S. SAXENA and M. C. JAIN, *Monatsh.*, 1969, **100**, 28.
2. R. S. SAXENA and O. P. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 9.
3. R. S. SAXENA and M. L. MITTAL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 2553.
4. L. H. BRIXNER and E. J. ABRAMSON, *Electro Chem.*, 1965, **112**, 70.
5. E. A. ARBIT and V. V. SEREBRONNIKOV, *Zhur. neorg. Khim.*, 1965, **10**, 410.
6. M. P. GLAZYRIN and A. A. IVEKIN, *Kristallografiya* 1964, **9**(6), 927.
7. R. S. SAXENA and O. P. SHARMA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28** 1881.
8. R. S. SAXENA and M. L. MITTAL, *Acta. Chim. Acad. Sci Hung.*, 1964, **40**, 109.
9. R. S. SAXENA and M. L. MITTAL, *Naturwiss*, 1964, **51**, 1.